

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

ANALYSIS OF THE CURRENT STATE OF ENGINEER VEHICLES AND EQUIPMENT AND PECULIARITIES OF THEIR MAINTENANCE AND REPAIR SYSTEM FUNCTIONING

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Abstract

The article is prepared on a topical issue related to maintaining the technical condition (TC) of engineer vehicles and equipment (EVE) in the process of its operation. The article analyzes the current state of EVE, as well as the features of their maintenance and repair system functioning.

Keywords: engineer vehicles and equipment; technical condition; maintenance; combat operations; combat mission; spare parts.

1. INTRODUCTION.

Successful performance of combat missions (CM) (including engineering support) entrusted to the units of the Armed Forces of Ukraine (AFU) significantly depends on TC of EVE.

These issues have become most urgent now during the Joint Forces Operation (JFO), as well as during the full-scale invasion of the Russian Federation troops.

Formulation of the problem. Analysis of the application of EVE in the area of JFO indicates an insufficient level of provision of repair units with necessary spare parts (SP) for maintenance and repair of EVE while carrying out tasks for the purposes intended.

Analysis of recent research and publications. When searching for scientific publications in this subject area, one cannot ignore the scientific works of V. Birkov [1], B. Demyanchuk [2], V. Sivak [3] and other researchers, who have quite deeply revealed most of the issues on this range of problems.

The purpose of the article. Conducting an analysis of the current state of EVE, as well as the peculiarities of the functioning of their maintenance and repair system during the performance of tasks as intended.

2. RESEARCH RESULTS.

When carrying out tasks, EVE is used, as a rule, in an integrated manner within the units of the Armed

Forces of Ukraine. At the same time, each item of equipment operates according to its intended purpose and technical characteristics. A characteristic feature of EVE is the variety of operating equipment and basic chassis. Therefore, taking into account the organization of EVE maintenance and repair, they should be considered as complex technical systems, the subsystems of which differ in functional purpose, as well as the nature of origin and occurrence of failures.

In accordance with the State Standard of Ukraine [4], the classification, nomenclature and characteristics of external operating factors that affect the reliability of EVE products throughout their life cycle are determined.

Thus, the analysis of the conducted research concerning EVE storage shows that climatic and biological factors have a significant impact on their reliability, in particular:

a) climatic factors: air temperature; relative humidity; precipitation (rain, snow); solar radiation, dust, sand; air pollution by corrosive compounds; atmospheric air pressure, wind;

b) biological factors: bacteria; mold and wood-destroying fungi; biological fouling; insects, worms, birds, rodents, etc.

The combination of climatic and biological factors influence on the state of EVE, over time leads to:

corrosion and aging of metal components of the product;

aging and destruction of non-metallic components of the product;

biological damage to both metal and non-metal components of the object [1].

All this, in turn, leads to a decrease in the level of EVE reliability during its intended use, as well as emergence of various types of failures. The intensity of the influence of these factors depends on the climatic conditions inherent in a particular physical and geographical area of the country.

It should be noted that in the process of operation, the technical condition of EVE, in the first place, depends on the storage of its components (systems).

Studies [1, 5] have shown that technical characteristics of such components as:

rubber technical products;

electrical equipment;

radio-electronic equipment;

and component parts that come into contact with fuels and lubricants and special liquids are subject to significant changes during the operation of EVE.

To achieve the required level of EVE maintenance and repair, it is necessary to take into account the fact that its state is characterized, on the one hand, by the internal state of the product, and on the other hand, by the influence of the external environment [4].

If the internal state of EVE depends on the degree of excellence established at the stage of development and production, then their maintenance and repair at the stage of operation depends on the availability of SP, the degree of training of crews and specialists of repair units, as well as other measures aimed at maintaining EVE in good working condition.

Thus, the maintenance and repair of EVE largely depends on the timely replacement of components during operation. Therefore, these circumstances should be taken into account in the reasonable nomenclature and number of SP and the set of EVE maintenance and repair works while carrying out the assigned tasks.

The experience of employing units of the Armed Forces of Ukraine shows that combat capabilities of units and subunits of engineer troops, and, accordingly, the completeness and timeliness of their tasks, fully depend on the degree of combat readiness of EVE. At the same time, the combat readiness of EVE is understood as the degree of their preparedness for employment while executing the CM.

Combat-ready EVE are considered to be such samples that have the required service life, brought to the initial state established by the operational documentation, and prepared to fulfill the assigned tasks, that is, to be used for the intended purpose [4, 5].

In the conditions of modern highly maneuverable combat operations (CO) and the enemy's powerful means of destruction, restoration of combat capability of engineering troops in the shortest possible time or maintaining it at a certain level, will depend on the clear organization and timely implementation of such an element of technical support as timely maintenance and repair of weapons and equipment directly in combat

formation of the Armed Forces of Ukraine units. Practically the only source of replenishment of EVE that failed during implementation of the CM will be their timely restoration by the system of mobile repair bodies of the engineer troops. At the same time, it should be considered that in this case, "military repair" and "restoration" are not synonymous. The concept of restoration is much broader, and includes not only the technological process of military repair, but also the search for damaged vehicles on the battlefield (in the places of their breakdowns), their evacuation to repair sites, delivery of vehicles to the unit (subunit) after repair, as well as transfer of faulty (damaged) samples that cannot be repaired in-house, to the superior officer's repair department.

There are concepts of "comprehensive repair" and "specialized repair", although without disclosing their content. However, for the correct organization of recovery, they need to be distinguished. During comprehensive repair the product being repaired, including EVE, is restored in a comprehensive manner, without dismemberment into partial elements in one repair body or by specialists of one service, or various services grouped in it organizationally or promptly.

During specialized repair, the product being repaired is divided into the main elements (base, engineering superstructure, machining facility), which are restored in different repair bodies, by specialists of the same service, which is the general contracting authority of the element.

Analysis of these provisions shows that the restoration of EVE during execution of the CM is a military repair performed under specific conditions. According to the experience of employing units of the Armed Forces of Ukraine, the average daily failure of EVE while carrying out CO was established (15-20% for individual groups of EVE). It follows that the restoration of damaged equipment in the course of CO is quite an important and, at the same time, challenging task.

However, it should be understood that the calculations of the expected number of damaged vehicles on the average daily percentage of losses can only be used when planning the operation for an approximate distribution of the order of available repair units and subunits engagement. More detailed information on the expected repair stock is needed in order to establish specific repair tasks and to make realistic assessment of recovery possibilities. The repair stock here refers to the number of vehicles that require repair at a given operational time.

To determine the tasks, repair bodies need to know the expected number of vehicles that can break down, labor intensity of their restoration by types of repairs, the percentage distribution of current repairs by intervals of labor intensity (in order to assess which part of it we are able to handle), as well as the nature and labor intensity of specialized work in different repair echelons (in order to assess the possibilities of their implementation with the existing composition of equipment sets).

The organization of repair works, in general, means the implementation by officials of a set of measures that ensure the effective solution by their subordinate repair subunits and units of the tasks for recovery of damaged EVE and their rapid return to working condition [5].

3. CONCLUSIONS AND PROSPECTS OF FURTHER RESEARCH.

It follows from the above that the EVE system needs improvement, because it functions under the influence of many factors.

To improve the EVE maintenance and repair system and develop recommendations for improving the efficiency of its functioning, it is necessary to analyze the factors that affect the functioning of the EVE maintenance and repair system.

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ВЛИЯНИЕ ЧИСТОТЫ ТОПЛИВА НА ТЕХНИЧЕСКО-ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКУЮ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ АВТОМОБИЛЯ

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INFLUENCE OF FUEL PURITY ON THE TECHNICAL AND ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF THE VEHICLE

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Аннотация

В статье даны выводы и рекомендации по определению влияния выбранной системы очистки топлива на технико-экономические показатели автомобильного транспорта на основе результатов испытаний, проведенных в условиях эксплуатации

Методы: Автомобильный транспорт имеет первостепенное значение среди всех транспортных средств. Следовательно, требуется его высокая надежность. Одним из способов повышения надежности является очистка топлива, поступающего в двигатель автомобиля. Для этого была разработана и экспериментально испытана система очистки топлива в жарких и пыльных условиях Узбекистана. Результаты испытаний были проанализированы с использованием электронных технологий и методов спектрального анализа. Определена степень износа деталей двигателя. Скорость износа деталей оценивалась методом спектрального анализа по количеству продуктов износа в моторном масле.

Полученные результаты: За счет усовершенствования системы очистки топлива износ деталей двигателя автомобилей сократился в 1,8 раза. Поэтому определение степени влияния качества очистки топлива на эффективность использования транспортного средства является одним из технически и экономически необходимым методом. Чем меньше значение индекса тонкой очистки топливного фильтра, тем больше загрязняющих веществ он будет удерживать в топливной композиции и тем чище будет топливо.

Вывод: В целом технико-экономическая эффективность эксплуатации автомобильного транспорта зависит от технического исправного состояния деталей и узлов автомобиля, их рабочих параметров, а также от оптимальных параметров работы системы очистки топлива.

Abstract

The article gives conclusions and recommendations for determining the influence of the selected fuel purification system on the technical and economic indicators of road transport based on the results of tests carried out under operating conditions.

Methods: Road transport is of paramount importance among all vehicles. Therefore, its high reliability is required. One way to improve reliability is to clean the fuel entering the car engine. For this purpose, a fuel purification system was developed and experimentally tested in the hot and dusty conditions of Uzbekistan. The test results were analyzed using electronic technology and spectral analysis methods. The degree of wear of engine parts is determined. The wear rate of parts was estimated by the method of spectral analysis by the amount of wear products in engine oil.